

The impact of promoting the concept of entrepreneurship in education colleges of different disciplines on entrepreneurial orientation

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Abstract: The capitalist system is focused on promoting entrepreneurship, especially among the youth who are in the stages of university education, being one of the most important factors of the economy. Entrepreneurs are considered of great importance in developed and developing countries. Such as establishing new business, and providing employment. Promoting entrepreneurship skills are the most important factor in the development of entrepreneurship, especially among university students outside the scope of business and economics colleges. Therefore this study will examine whether education colleges has an effect on individuals to start their own business after education specially there are a huge number of graduates from education college and are unemployed after graduation. In this study, a survey research was conducted to determine the thoughts of students from Education College about starting their own business and the tendencies of university students with and without entrepreneurship education to be entrepreneurs were compared. To achieve this goal, a total of 152 students who took or did not take entrepreneurship courses in the college of education were surveyed through a the questionnaires, that examine the level of knowledge of the students about entrepreneurship, their interest in establishing their own business, the underlying reasons for wishing to be entrepreneurs and the factors preventing them from being an entrepreneur were also determined. According to the results of the research, students having entrepreneurship skills are more thinking of starting their own business than those who do not have entrepreneurship skills. Entrepreneurship educators are more interested in starting their own business and intend to push.

Keywords: entrepreneurship, entrepreneur, business education, Education College

I. Introduction

Entrepreneurship can be considered as the most important engine of economic growth. With entrepreneurs, the economy will achieve high levels of innovation, productivity in production, new employment, and productivity growth. Therefore companies' ability to excel in competition depends on their realization of their entrepreneurial potential. Taking into account that, development of entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial success do not happen by chance. Entrepreneurs exist with the characteristics of their own communities, even transnational economies and societies. This environment, consist of resources, infrastructure and attitudes, forms the ecosystem of entrepreneurship.

The entrepreneurship factor, as an extension of innovativeness for development and progress since the beginning of human history, has been very important throughout all periods, although it has been defined recently. As the activities of people to meet their unlimited needs. Along with the increase in the diversity of human needs, there has been an increase in the variety of works from different discipline. With this

diversification, the necessity of competition conditions has started to emerge. Thus, with the development of competitive conditions, the development process of entrepreneurship has started to accelerate (Umihanic et al 2017). Whereas entrepreneur can be defined as an economic agent that recognizes the new needs of human beings, manages to produce the same goods or services with new and more efficient methods, or increases productivity through a new form of organization or specifically transforms inventions into innovation. The entrepreneur, who has a strong desire to succeed, constantly creates new ideas and enjoys producing better.

One of the common debates is about whether entrepreneurship is an innate talent. The common belief in this direction is that entrepreneurship is a feature gained through education rather than being an innate talent. Therefore, in order to increase entrepreneurship tendency, we can contribute to the increase of entrepreneurship characteristics of economic agents by expanding the relevant education. Education can contribute to increasing the skill of entrepreneurs, as entrepreneurship education contributes to the skill of entrepreneurs at all levels (Barba & Atienza 2016).

The growth and development levels of the countries are primarily measured by national income or per capita income. At the same time, the level of development and growth has started to be explained by a healthy and long-lived life, human capital, which expresses the rate of educated manpower in one direction. Education is one of the most important components of human capital. Therefore education can mean both increasing entrepreneurship skills and increasing human capital. Especially in the literature, the impact of human capital on growth and development is highly emphasized. It is a common point in the literature that developments in the field of education increase productivity, especially in technology, and can increase productivity, and thus affect economic growth (Lina, et al, 2019).

The two most important factors that will support entrepreneurship are the right skills to turn motivation and opportunities into a successful small business enterprise, so that individuals can become entrepreneurs. The education to be provided in this direction will enable to reveal the entrepreneurial potential and strengthen their talents. However the main goal of the College of Education in Palestinian universities lies in preparing qualified cadres of educators, teachers and mentors in the fields of educational, psychological and instructional sciences, in keeping with contemporary educational, professional and technical developments. Although it could be seen the field of colleges of education is completely far from other fields of colleges, especially colleges of administrative and economic sciences, which are considered a fertile environment for developing the skills of entrepreneurs (Barba & Atienza, 2016). Given the increasing number of graduates from colleges of education, and the limited absorption of the labor market for these graduates, the skills of entrepreneurs in colleges of education can be developed by focusing on elective courses from the faculties of administrative and economic sciences. Others mean that it is not about launching a new business, but rather about making graduates more creative, opportunity-oriented, proactive and innovative, and upholding a broad definition of entrepreneurship that is relevant to all walks of life.

All students in the College of Education can and must train their ability and willingness to create value for their own and for other people. This could be achieved at the heart of entrepreneurship and also can be considered a competency that all people increasingly need in today's society, regardless of career choice. The creation of new businesses is then seen as one of many different ways for creating value. In this study, primarily promoting the concept of entrepreneurship in education colleges of different disciplines on entrepreneurial orientation will be discussed. After discussing the impact of education on entrepreneurship, the results of the questionnaire applied to the fourth year students of the faculty of education were evaluated. Finally, conclusion and recommendations were made by making a general evaluation (Packham, et al 2010).

II. Concept of Entrepreneurship

It is not possible to make a single definition for the concept of entrepreneurship. We see for the first time that Richard Cantillon described as the person who does business under entrepreneurial uncertainty. William

Stanley Jevons called him the pioneer of new roads. Of course, many economic thinkers put forward their ideas on the entrepreneur, while Joseph Alois Schumpeter drew attention to the innovative entrepreneur (Daft, 2005).

Entrepreneurship, which is shown as the basic dynamics of economic development, is the process of organizing the necessary resources to start a business venture and anticipating risks and gains related to this business. When we consider economic agents acting in accordance with today's modern and innovative understanding, the concept of entrepreneurship can be explained by concepts such as flexibility, profit-oriented, innovation, creativity and being focused on change. When we consider these concepts, we can see why the economy is the basic dynamics. On the other side if development means increase in production, therefore the increase in national income, innovation and entrepreneurship will mean that the growth of the economy is the main dynamics, since it is the production of new goods and services or the increase in productivity (Pittaway, & Cope, 2007).

Explaining entrepreneurship as a process that changes businesses and products for a better situation, Schumpeter stated that entrepreneurship is a destructive entrepreneurship by specifying the creative demolition feature of the economy and destroying the existing economic order (Coulter 2001).

According to Schumpeter, innovation is at the core of entrepreneurship. Seeing entrepreneurship as a way of thinking that emerges at the level of decision making in the business world, Schumpeter stated the important feature of this idea as following the innovations and placing these innovations on the market for the needs of the society (Śledzik, 2013).

Others has shown entrepreneurship as a tool that tries to realize new welfare creation and distribution of welfare phenomena which are shown as important in social development (Nabi, et al 2017).

Especially when we look at the definitions of entrepreneurship in all sources, we see that the most important definition by Hisrich, entrepreneurship is the process of creating a different value by taking time and effort by taking psychological, economic and social risks. At the end of this process, people satisfy their personal desires and reach satisfaction. The process of creating new knowledge in this direction will be defined as entrepreneurship (Hisrich and Peters 2001).

Others define entrepreneurship as a whole of activities that work under the influence of the social, cultural, political and economic environments in which people are involved in evaluating the opportunities that arise in the markets (Amornpinyo, 2018).

Entrepreneurship can emerge when many factors come together. Individuals with high entrepreneurship tendencies are also an important factor in the emergence of entrepreneurship in an environment where entrepreneurship activity is supported. We can say that the combination of society, motivation, human capital, network capital, psychological characteristics, demography, and sectorial structure with the person, especially the family, will reveal the entrepreneur. Education can be the most important factor for young people and women to become entrepreneurs. Therefore, the perception that the important thing for entrepreneurship is only capital is not true. What is more important than capital is to have intellectual capital (Brennan, et al 2003)

III. Entrepreneurship and Economic Growth

For the first time, we see that Adam Smith associates economic growth, which is the most important subject of economics, with education. According to Smith, the accumulation obtained as a result of the education received will naturally be capital accumulation and the society will benefit from this accumulation (Martin, et al 2012). On the other hand human capital accumulation is the source of growth and will ensure that growth is sustainable. Undoubtedly, human capital can be continuously increased by education. In the same direction, it is the source of innovations that provide new goods and services is the human capital. (Cetindamar, et al 2012).

When we look at the different growth theories and literature in this direction, technology, inventions, patents, new ideas, innovations or new forms of regulation provide economic growth. It will create an overflow effect by increasing the efficiency of accumulated working capital and increasing enterprise innovation (Saraf, 2015).

Innovation and entrepreneurship, which are important for developing economies, are seen as the way to use unused resources, increase national income by producing goods and services, and earn more profit by innovating. Entrepreneurship and innovation will play an important role both in the growth and development of the economy and in the growth and development of the country. In addition to these features, it will contribute to increasing job opportunities in the business fields that in return it will create entrepreneurship. Adding to this, contribution of entrepreneurs to the society cannot be denied in this direction because they increase the social welfare level and quality of life, using the unused potentials and increase the production of goods and services, while leading the development of science and technology with their innovative character. Increasing number of enterprises due to increasing entrepreneurship will also contribute to increase job opportunities rate. Entrepreneurs that increase economic growth will enable more entrepreneurs to appear. On the same line it could be stated that entrepreneur ensures that resources are transferred from lowefficiency areas to high areas for use in eliminating unlimited needs. It is the person who thinks that the scarce resources to be used for entrepreneurial production should be produced in a way to provide the highest benefit. Those who take risks with new goods or services in new markets, realizing the new production method, organization, goods or services, industry, technology or entrepreneurial opportunities that bring them all together. Therefore it could be said that, entrepreneurship is an important factor for economic growth and development (Kirkley, 2017).

IV. Entrepreneurship and Education

The access to information and the transition to the information society have enabled entrepreneurship research to accelerate by causing the entrepreneurship to gain importance and being seen as the driving force of the economy. One of the main topics of the researches is entrepreneurship education, which is seen as one of the most important factors in uncovering entrepreneurial potential (Schmitz, 2017). One of the most important reasons for entrepreneurship education as a prominent subject is not only the entrepreneurship but also some individual features; at the same time, it is realized that it can be brought into the individual with the effect of education and environment (UNCTAD, 2010). It is a well-known fact that individual characteristics constitute some of the features required in the formation of entrepreneurship. However, besides the individual characteristics, the values that will be gained to the individual through education will enable them to reveal the properties that exist in the individual but are not yet recognized. For this reason, it would not be wrong to say that the effect of education on entrepreneurship is quite large (Yun & Lee, 2018). Preparation, dissemination of education programs that support entrepreneurship and the use of game tactics in the implementation of these programs, and supporting learning will be extremely important in the education of successful entrepreneurs. In this way, entrepreneurship is perceived as a career and will contribute positively to the healthy development of small businesses, and bringing successful entrepreneurs will be one of the cornerstones of the revival of the economy (Fayolle et al 2006).

Providing entrepreneurship education to individuals with a business idea and entrepreneurial spirit before starting any initiative is extremely important in terms of increasing the chances of success of individuals' future initiatives. It is stated that especially in the formation of entrepreneurial and attitudinal behaviors of young people, entrepreneurship education is of great importance, it helps to reveal entrepreneurship potential of students and directs young people to start their own businesses. Educational institutions are very important in establishing an entrepreneurship culture, teaching entrepreneurship and putting it into practice effectively. Data on creating entrepreneurship awareness of the students by the educational institutions, providing education on the development of entrepreneurial characteristics, creating the environments where business professionals and students can come together showing a strong relationship between entrepreneurship and education (Küttima, 2014). Entrepreneurship education is a process that can differ according to the age, education background,

interests and expectations of the individual, and entrepreneurship can be taught to individuals in different environments with different methods. While entrepreneurship education is provided to individuals with some skills, it is aimed to develop some skills that already exist in individuals. Among the skills that individuals can develop with education are skills such as risk taking, taking responsibility and managing skills. In addition, the skills to be gained through vocational training are important in terms of both being entrepreneurs, and providing quality from talented individual and well-educated workforce to entrepreneurs. On the other hand, it should not be forgotten that different skills should be at the forefront for different stages of the entrepreneurship process (Innocent, 2019).

Today, entrepreneurship education are taught by universities with formal education, but they are also given by widespread education by different institutions and organizations in order to guide people who have an idea, want to start their own business or are interested in entrepreneurship and to gain the necessary skills (Rauch &Hulsink, 2015).

From the foregoing it could be emphasized that human capital is made up of education, past experiences and special knowledge, and this is the most important factor for the success of entrepreneurship. Based on this, we can emphasize the importance of the relationship between general education and entrepreneurship. At the same time, the education given to increase human capital in general, and human capital within the framework of entrepreneurship has a different meaning than formal education. Education should be designed to support entrepreneurship, especially to bring out entrepreneurship. Today's entrepreneurs are obligated to overcome the identity and image of the classic entrepreneur. These new entrepreneurtype of organizations, which is called IT entrepreneurs, will be the most important driving force in national and international competition. Considering the transformative effect of information technologies on business in general and entrepreneurship styles in particular; The rational application of the principles of knowledge management in the knowledge based business world will enable IT entrepreneurs to be educated (UNCTAD, 2010).

Education, which affects individual characteristics such as personality, makes it more important and increases the success of entrepreneurs. Education also expresses a field of development that the person can manage. Without knowledge, entrepreneurship cannot be combined with a strategy. Many entrepreneurs need training in the areas of management, finance, planning and marketing. It is an inevitable requirement to increase the equipment related to the enterprise for the education of individual and corporate entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurship education will contribute positively to the thinking of entrepreneurship as a career and to the healthy development of small businesses (Henderson & Robertson, 1999). The purpose of entrepreneurship education is to reveal the entrepreneurial qualities that exist in the person but remain hidden. At the same time, education provided to entrepreneurs prevents them from doing wrong things and prevents waste of production resources such as capital, labor and natural resources. Entrepreneurship education; supporting and promoting entrepreneurship and entrepreneurship therefore is an important factor in the development of entrepreneurship. Aware of this is happening at universities all over the world, regarding the delivery of this education. In addition to entrepreneurship education programs that rapidly progress at all levels of the education system, the increase in the number of courses, academics and entrepreneurship programs offered in the field of entrepreneurship is an indicator of this situation (Westhead&Solesvik, 2016). The idea that issues such as creating solutions to the unemployment problem, sustaining the general balance of the economy and reducing budget deficits will be possible with the development of entrepreneurship has made entrepreneurship education one of the most strategic issues (Fayolle&Gailly, (2015).

In addition to the positive effects of entrepreneurship education on an individual and business basis, macro effects on a country basis, in other words, are very important. The development of entrepreneurship which plays an important role in economic development of countries especially for employment and innovation. With entrepreneurship education, it is aimed to inform individuals about entrepreneurship as a very attractive option, to motivate entrepreneur candidates and entrepreneurs in this direction and to provide individuals with the necessary knowledge and skills (Caroline et al 2017).

Placing this awareness in students and giving detailed information about entrepreneurship will be guiding how they will reach the capital required for entrepreneurship. People will increase their knowledge and skills about being a good entrepreneur as a result of their education (Leal-Rodriguez et al 2018).

V. Methodology and Findings

The aim of this study is to determine the impact of promoting the concept of entrepreneurship in education colleges of different disciplines on entrepreneurial orientation. Questionnaire method was used to collect data to be used in the research. In order to determine the concept of entrepreneurship in education colleges, respondents were asked to answer 42 questions. The study was carried out on the fourth level of students of the Faculty of Education of Al-Quds Open University. A total of 152 students participated in the survey. The scale was used in the questionnaire and analyzed for the data obtained.

Table1: Descriptive statistics of entrepreneurship orientation domains, N= 152

Domain	Mean	SD	Variation
Attitude Towards Behavior	4.01	0.61	0.15
Perceived Norms of Social Behavior	3.64	0.63	0.17
Perceived Behavioral Control	3.77	0.65	0.17
General Tendency toward Entrepreneurship	3.84	0.74	0.19
Entrepreneurship Information	3.88	0.71	0.18
Entrepreneurship Skills	3.85	0.72	0.19

It could be seen from table above that all domains ranked high score. As indicated by the mean average $m=4.01$ for attitude toward behavior, $m= 3.64$ for perceived norms of social behavior, $m= 3.77$ for perceived behavioral control, $m= 3.84$ for general tendency toward entrepreneurship, $m=3.88$ for entrepreneurship information, and $m=3.85$ for entrepreneurship skills. Indicating a high score for all mentioned domains for students participated in this study, with regards to the high level of entrepreneurial tendency. Therefore it could be said that “attitudes toward behavior” self-standard indicated that some respondents looked at other key people in their lives such as their friend, relatives, teachers, who believed they had not performed entrepreneurial behavior. This may be due to the failure of friends or relatives in some aspects to increase students' attitudes towards behavior. However with regards to general tendency toward entrepreneurship it indicates that some students were in the intermediate stage and imagined that they were able to perform behavior that specifically referred to entrepreneurship. Hence, the way relatives and friends can build interest among themselves to become prominent future entrepreneurs must be sponsored. Whereas the perceived behavioral control indicated that some of the respondents already have almost half of the positive evaluation towards their performance of entrepreneurial behavior within themselves. This support the entrepreneurship information and entrepreneurship skills whereit was noted that the participants in the study enjoy the knowledge and experience as a result of the courses they received regarding entrepreneurship while learning during their study period despite their different specializations.

By examining the coefficient variance of standard deviation it could be noted that the variation between the respondents of the domains in this study ranged from 15% to 19%, an acceptable ration between the opinion of their responses. Although some respondents register high score closed to the highest score of five, that indicates the entrepreneurial intention indicated that some of the respondents highly perceived that they placed full efforts to carry out entrepreneurial behavior. Similarly, the maximum score of 5.00 were reported for all the predictors. As they indicated they fully can performed their attitude towards entrepreneur, and believed that their capabilities to produce entrepreneur's performance was at the full level. This implied that some of the respondents perceived other key people in their lives such as relatives, friends, teachers believed they are fully performed the behavior that related to entrepreneurial.

Table 2: correlation analysis between entrepreneurship orientation independent variable, N=152

Domains	Person Correlation	Sig. (2-tailed)
Attitude towards Behavior	0.232**	0.00
perceived norms of social behavior	0.333**	0.00
perceived behavioral control	0.252**	0.00
general tendency toward entrepreneurship	0.335**	0.00
entrepreneurship information	0.332**	0.00
entrepreneurship skills	0.351**	0.00

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

In order to analyze the relationship between the domain variables (attitudes toward behavior, perceived norms of social behavior, perceived behavioral control, general tendency toward entrepreneurship, entrepreneurship information and entrepreneurship skills) with entrepreneurship orientation.

As seen in table 2, the correlation between the variable showed bivariate relationship with entrepreneurship orientation. As seen from the table all six domains (attitudes toward behavior, perceived norms of social behavior, perceived behavioral control, general tendency toward entrepreneurship, entrepreneurship information and entrepreneurship skills) are significantly correlated with entrepreneurship orientation ($r=0.232$, $p<0.01$), ($r=0.333$, $p<0.01$), ($r=0.252$, $p<0.01$), ($r=0.335$, $p<0.01$), ($r=0.332$, $p<0.01$), ($r=0.351$, $p<0.01$). The researcher's interpretation of this correlation is explained by the homogeneity of the categories of the subjects respondents in the College of Education.

Table 3: Regression Analysis between independent variable and entrepreneurship orientation, N=152, R²=0.189, F=11.732

	Beta	t-Ratio	Sig.
Attitude Towards Behavior	0.073	0.725	0.398
Perceived Norms of Social Behavior	0.314	3.787	0.000
Perceived Behavioral Control	0.063	0.669	0.421
General Tendency	0.324	3.541	0.000

toward Entrepreneurship			
Entrepreneurship Information	0.325	3.791	0.000
Entrepreneurship Skills	0.079	0.812	0.496

**Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level
 (2-tailed).

As presented in table 3, the regression analysis for measuring which variables among the six domains (attitudes toward behavior, perceived norms of social behavior, perceived behavioral control, general tendency toward entrepreneurship, entrepreneurship information and entrepreneurship skills) have influence on the level of entrepreneurship orientation among the respondents of this research. This is evident as shown in table 3, that ($R^2=0.189$, $F=11.732$) of the variance in entrepreneurial orientation can be interpreted and explained by the attitudes toward behavior, perceived norms of social behavior, perceived behavioral control, general tendency toward entrepreneurship, entrepreneurship information and entrepreneurship skills, that three of the mentioned domains namely: (Perceived Norms of Social Behavior, General Tendency toward Entrepreneurship, and Entrepreneurship Information) are significantly related to entrepreneurship orientation as evident by ($B=0.314$ $P=0.000$), ($B=0.324$, $P=0.000$) and ($B=0.325$, $P=0.000$) respectively, whereas (Attitude Towards Behavior, Perceived Behavioral Control, and Entrepreneurship Skills) with ($B=0.073$, $P=0.452$), ($B=0.063$, $P=0.398$) and ($B=0.079$, $P=0.496$) respectively has no significant relation towards students entrepreneurial orientation.

VI. Conclusion and Recommendations

The rapid technological progress unemployment that has been experienced with the radical change with globalization has become an important problem especially for developing countries. In order to reduce unemployment, it is necessary to make efforts in raising entrepreneurs to increase the number of entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurship plays an important role in promoting economic growth. Countries that support entrepreneurship invest in both entrepreneurship education and their future. When the structure of countries with intensive entrepreneurship is examined, it is seen that these countries are also ahead in terms of economic growth and development. Therefore in this study the discussion has been conducted with the dependent variable “the entrepreneurship orientation” and the independent variable which consist of (attitudes toward behavior, perceived norms of social behavior, perceived behavioral control, general tendency toward entrepreneurship, entrepreneurship information and entrepreneurship skills). The discussion arises each variable continuously among practitioners and there may be ongoing research that will be done to verifying the impact of some variables towards the entrepreneurship orientation. Noting that an entrepreneur can be a type of profession that involves many difficult tasks compared to other common occupations. This study gives some insights into what drives the respondents from the college of education to decide on taking a courses that pertain to entrepreneurship in parallel to their own study tract as part of the elements of entrepreneurship. Since these days can be called as life of a better competition, therefore the intention of entrepreneurship is a good phenomenon that should be encouraged among young people to deal with the hectic lifestyle and needs of in the era of competition. Entrepreneurship can be a lifesaver for reducing the ratio of unemployment rate because it does not affects one individual only but there will be opportunities to create new jobs, thus self-employments can be increased .

The study found that “Perceived norms of social behavior, general tendency toward entrepreneurship, and entrepreneurship information” are significantly related to entrepreneurship orientation, whereas the other three domains as part of the independent variable of this study namely: “attitude towards behavior, perceived behavioral control, and entrepreneurship skills” are not significantly related, this was supported by several studies (Baet al 2014), (Basardien et al, 2016) which have mutual findings with entrepreneurship orientation.

As they found a statistical significant relationship between a stimulus that is a personal measure of entrepreneurship orientation of such initiatives. Consequently, it can be said that the surrounding people are interconnected in influencing these individuals in the entrepreneurship orientation to reinforce the success of their future project line. They act as they want others to see them, such as parents support and friend encouragement to influence their thinking to choose the best line to join in the business context. Whereas the other three domains (perceived norms of social behavior, perceived behavioral control, and entrepreneurship information) that have a significant relationship to the entrepreneurship orientation may lead by the influences on several factors such as; awareness of an entrepreneurial path, supporting business networks and the role-play (Fayolle, 2015). in addition to the education students take, the family background and surrounding can play some important role as these variables expose individuals to the entrepreneurship orientation at an early age (Hagg&Kurzewska (2016). also it can be said that encouragement to the orientation of entrepreneurship might be facilitated by connection with surrounding entrepreneurs, which in return can put together students with entrepreneurial aspirations, engaging with the business activities during internship or getting in touch with university staff with an entrepreneurial spirit. however Hattab, 2015)found no significant relationship between perceived norms of social behavior and entrepreneurship orientation among students of Greek University. it was also found that perceived norms of social behavior and entrepreneurship orientation among Chinese students in Shanghai. Similarly, the findings of (Hussain, 2015)found that perceived norms of social behavior does not associate to entrepreneurial intention among students. The an related significant relationships might be as a cause of some environmental factors that affects the respondents to be entrepreneurs in the future. However, the other three domains of the independent variable which refer to attitude towards behavior and perceived behavioral control and entrepreneurship skills did not related to entrepreneurship orientation. This was supported by (Krithika&Venkatachalam, 2014) with no significant relationship between attitude towards behavior, perceived behavioral control and entrepreneurship orientation on his study. Additionally previous researchers such as (Kuttim et al, 2014) suggested that the entrepreneurship orientation could begin with the individual decision to put themselves in the challenge circle, especially for individuals wishing to be self-employed rather than putting themselves in the list of unemployment. taking into consideration real work environment might be limited to job opportunities (Mahendra et al, 2017). whereas (Malebana&Swanepel, 2014) stated that individual's attitude towards entrepreneurship relies on external factors such as education and previous experience. Adding that entrepreneurship education are provided in educational institutions to identify potential entrepreneurs and find ways to bring them to the field. The more the number of individuals with a country's entrepreneurial qualifications, the more successful it will be in economic growth and development. Therefore it can be said that Individuals should be motivated to improve their entrepreneurial skills, and to enhance students' training methods and materials in entrepreneurial courses so that they can increase their knowledge toward the direction of entrepreneurship (Mohammed et al, 2017). In addition, other public institutions such as the Ministry of Higher Education, the Ministry of Economy and Trade, etc., should encourage and help students to engage them in the field of entrepreneurship, through various approaches such as giving tax holidays, easy financial loans, and other incentive programs. Noting that entrepreneurs who are prone to success; economic agents that stand up to difficulties, do their job best, use their talents and are independent. The entrepreneur is after the success reward, the profit that they will receive using these talents will be increased. To keep profit, which is the reward of success, at the highest level, it has to improve themselves and equip it with a certain burden of knowledge. The education to be given in educational institutions has increased for the entrepreneur, who must receive continuous training to access this information.

In the end it can be said that; students who have received entrepreneurship education have more tendency to entrepreneurship after the graduation, differ from those who have not received entrepreneurship education. Taking into consideration that entrepreneurship is an important career opportunity for all economic agents who have recently graduated from the university, and the entrepreneurship education they receive will bring out the entrepreneurial spirit that exists within the people. In order to transform this entrepreneurial spirit into a successful entrepreneurship activity, institutions and organizations providing entrepreneurship education have a lot of responsibilities. In order for these institutions to fulfill their duties, they should be supported more by the

university, and other related institutions such as the ministry of higher education, as part of stimulating economic development, this in return will lead to a stable economic growth.

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